

SURFACE ANALYSES OF BASALT FIBRES: TAILORING THE INTERPHASE OF “GREEN” FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

In times of raw material scarcity, the efficient exploitation of raw materials, as well as the reclamation of materials post-use, get more and more in focus for high performance material design.

The perceptions of renewable fibres for reinforcement are predominantly connected with jute, flax and hemp due to the manner of reaping and growing of plants. However, the genesis of magmatic rocks is a similarly renewable process. With each eruption of a volcano, rocks like basalt are generated when lava cools down quickly at the Earth’s surface, so it seems to be an inexhaustible raw material source. The disadvantage of natural fibres is the dependence of mechanical and other properties on environmental conditions during the growing phase. Basalt fibres are not affected by such factors: instead, as with glass fibres, the quality strongly depends on the processing technology. According Novitskii and Efremov [1] two techniques are available: modular and multioperator technology, which differ in the size of bath furnace and number of spinneret feeders. Nevertheless, fiberizing itself is a complex process, which is affected by multiple factors. Next to the melting and drawing process, sizing plays an important role. Therefore, fundamental studies of fibre surfaces are advantageous for tailored sizing and/or interphase development [2].

Dealing with surface sensitive methods enables manifold sources to provide additional information on the decomposition of glass structures. Fig. 1 gives a summary of surface analysis methods and

their expected outcome for fibre development as well as interphase design. Thus, these methods provide the basis for comprehensive investigation of fibres themselves and sizings (aqueous formulations of assorted components, including, coupling agents, film formers, lubricants and other additives) applied to them. Sizings are important not only for the role they carry out protecting the surface layer during the fibre manufacture, but also for the effect they have on the properties of subsequent composites [3]. The review of Ishida [4] comprehensively reflected fundamental understanding of molecular and micro structure of interfaces and interphases in composites and coatings.

Fig. 1. Summary of surface analysis methods and their expected outcome for fibre development as well as interphase design.

The concepts of an interphase containing chemisorbed and physisorbed silane as well as that of an inter-diffusion and inter-penetrating polymer network (IPN) formation on sizing/matrix interfaces are well known [4, 5].

Coupling agents used in fibre sizings are predominantly organosilanes combining two types of functionality: a silicon-functional group and an organofunctional group. The silicon functional group is a hydrolyzable group responsible for the bond to the glass surface, whereas the organofunctional group reacts or interacts with the polymeric matrix.

Due to hydrolysis, reactive silanol groups are generated which condense with other silanol groups, including silanol groups on the fibre surface. A stable covalent linkage is formed by drying or curing [6-9]. According to Arkles [8], formation of stable condensation products is also possible with oxides of e.g. aluminium, zirconium and titanium; less stable bonds are formed with oxides of boron, iron, carbon and no stable bond formation is expected with Si-O- and alkali metal oxides or carbonates.

In this work, the composition of the surfaces of unsized, silanized and temperature treated basalt fibres are studied by XPS. Based on the work of Thomason and Dwight [10] the coverage of a surface by the applied coupling agents is discussed, as well as the bonding behaviour of coupling agents on the basalt surface itself. Furthermore, the influence of a thermal treatment on the surface of two basalt fibres with a different chemical composition is investigated.

2 Experimental

Several surface treated basalt fibres are investigated by XPS, and SEM techniques. Surface treatment includes unsized as well as silanized state and heat treatment (600°C/5h).

Two fibres, BAS11 and BAS12, were manufactured using an industrial scale pilot plant; chemical composition is given in Tab.1. The nominal diameter of the basalt fibres is 15 µm and the nominal yarn count is 100 tex. The unsized state is achieved by sizing only with water during the drawing process. Fibres were sized with an aqueous solution of

commercial silanes. Investigated silane coupling agents are S1: N-2-(vinylbenzylamino)-ethyl-3-aminopropyl-trimethoxysilane (Z-6032 supplied by Dow Corning), S3: amino-functional silane (A-1128 supplied by Momentive) and S5: 3-glycidyloxypropyl-trimethoxysilane (GLYMO supplied by Evonik). The average sizing content on fibres is ≤0.1wt % determined by pyrolysis (650°C/1h).

XPS analyses were performed on a ThermoFisher Scientific (East Grinstead, UK) Theta Probe spectrometer. XPS spectra were acquired using a monochromated Al K α X-ray source (hv = 1486.6 eV). An X-ray spot of 400 µm radius was employed. Survey spectra were acquired employing a pass energy of 300 eV. High resolution, core level spectra for O1s, C1s, Al2p, Na1s, Si2p, Ca2p, Mg1s and Ti2p were acquired using a pass energy of 50 eV, Fe2p core level spectra were acquired with a pass energy of 80 eV.

Heat treatment was managed by storing fibres in an oven (L5/11 Nabatherm) for 5h at 500°C and 600°C in air.

For qualitative filament surface investigation, a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Ultra Plus (Zeiss, Germany) was used. Specimens were sputter-coated with platinum.

Single fibre tensile tests were conducted under air-conditioning (temperature 23°C, rel. humidity 50 %) by using a Favigraph semi-automatic testing device (Textechno, Mönchengladbach, Germany) equipped with a 1 N load cell. The cross head velocity was 25 mm/min and the gauge length was 50 mm. The fineness of each selected fibre was determined by using the vibroscope method in accordance with ASTM D 1577. 50 single fibres were tested for the determination of the average values with exception of data point BAS 12 – 600°C/5h. Here, fibres were extensively weakened by thermal treatment. Therefore, only 20 single fibres were tested (Fig. 5 – unfilled diamond).

Tensile test results were evaluated by Weibull probability analysis according to Eq.1, where P is the cumulative probability of failure of filament at the applied stress σ .

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m} \quad (1)$$

The scale parameter σ_0 represents the stress at which 63.2% of the filaments break ($P(\sigma_0) = 0.6321$). The shape parameter m , designated as Weibull modulus, is a measure of the distribution of the failure stress. A higher value of m indicates that filaments fail in a narrower range of failure stresses. Weibull parameters are determined by plotting $\ln(-\ln(1 - P))$ against $\ln(\sigma)$. Thereby, m is equal to the slope of the generated curve and σ_0 is equal to interception with $\ln(-\ln(1 - P)) = 0$.

$P_i = (i - 0.5)/N$ is used to calculate the probability of the failure P_i for the i th strength. N is the sample size. Eq. 1 is used to evaluate a unimodal Weibull distribution.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Chemical composition of basalt fibres

Typical compositions of available continuous basalt fibres are about 52-61 wt% RO_2 , 21-31wt% R_2O_3

and 13-21 wt% $RO+R_2O$. Basalt fibres contain up to one fifth oxides, which may act as modifiers in the glass network ($RO+R_2O$). The main component is silica. Other components, in order of their amount, are oxides of aluminium, iron, calcium, magnesium, as well as sodium, potassium and titanium. Basalt fibres are free of boron. Tab. 1 shows exemplary chemical composition of 2 analyzed continuous basalt fibres. BAS12 fibre compared to BAS11 fibre is poorer in silica, but richer in magnesium and iron oxide.

Tab.1. Chemical composition of basalt fibres in wt%

	BAS11	BAS12
SiO ₂	58	52
Al ₂ O ₃	18	17
Fe ₂ O ₃ *	7	10
CaO	7	8
MgO	3	6
Na ₂ O+K ₂ O	5	5
TiO ₂	1	2

*includes FeO and Fe₂O₃

Fig. 2. XPS Survey spectra of unsized BAS11 and BAS12 fibre

3.2 Surface constitution

The chemical composition of fibre surfaces of BAS11 and BAS12 fibre is investigated by XPS. Fig. 2 shows the survey spectra. Fig. 3a displays the main components as a ratio of atomic-concentrations. Detected elements are: silicon, aluminium, iron, calcium, magnesium and sodium. (Titanium is detected in negligible quantities and therefore not displayed in Fig. 3a).

The fibre surface is contaminated by carbon. C/Si ratio of BAS12 is higher than BAS11 fibre but still classified as unsized fibre due to a C/Si ratio of about 3 according to Thomason’s rule of thumb for evaluating sizing coverage [10]. The surface layer is rich in silicon, aluminium and, in the case of BAS12 fibres, in magnesium. In spite of the higher content of iron oxide compared to magnesium oxides, the iron oxides seem to be not predominate at the fibre surface. Fe/Si ratio is 0.1 (BAS11) and 0.16 (BAS12), whereas Al/Si ratio is increased: 0.30 (BAS11) and 0.26 (BAS12).

Fig. 3b and 3c display results of high resolution scans of the silane treated basalt fibres. Due to the applied silane coupling agents containing Si, coverage of silanized basalt fibres cannot be discussed in terms of the C/Si ratio. Therefore, the detected atomic concentrations of Si, O, N and C are related to several elements, which are characteristic for basalt fibres. These are Ca, Al and Fe. The coverage by coupling agents is detectable by increased atomic concentrations of C, Si and partly N.

In contrast to well-known and established E-glass fibres, basalt fibres contain higher amounts of iron oxides. Nevertheless, a similarity in chemical composition of E-glass and Basalt fibres has been reported by Park and Subramanian [11]. Obtained XPS results indicate relatively high intensities of Si and Al. Oxides of silicon and aluminium are able to form stable bonds with silanol groups of coupling agent. Therefore, it is proposed that characteristic Fe- content of basalt fibres plays a minor role for covalent bond formation and/or build up the polysiloxane layer.

Fig. 3. XPS data: Chemical composition of basalt fibres surface displayed as ratio of atomic concentrations (a) unsized BAS11 and BAS12 fibres; X/O ratio with X=Si, Al, Fe, Ca, Mg or Na (b) unsized and silane treated BAS11 fibre; X/Fe ratio with X=Si, C,O or N (c) unsized and silane treated BAS11 fibre; X/Al ratio with X=Si, C,O or N

Fig. 4 shows N1s spectra of S1 and S3 treated basalt fibres. Both coupling agents are amino- functional silanes. N indicates an amino group able to form hydrogen bonds with OH groups at the fibre surface itself [5] influencing the structure of the polysiloxane layer. According to Arora et al. [12] the XPS ratio N/Ca is a useful indicator of glass fibre coverage. In our experiment the N/Fe and N/Al ratio were determined as both elements are more characteristic for basalt glass. Calculated values are N/Al = 0.8 and N/Fe= 3.9 for S1 treated fibre and N/Al = 1.2 and N/Fe= 4.8 for S3 treated fibre. Furthermore, the N1s spectra of S1 and S3 are distinguished from each other. A peak at 399.9 eV and 399.6 eV is observed, respectively. Closer examinations of the photoelectron peak of S3 treated fibre reveals a shoulder at higher binding energy (BE) at approximately 402 eV. BE of 399.6 eV is assigned to free amino groups (-NH₂) [13], 399.9 eV to NH [12], whereas occurrence of peak shoulder is probably caused by protonated amino groups.

Fig. 3b and 3c show that the highest degree of surface coverage is obtained by S3 silane treatment due to C/X (X= Fe or Al) ratio is the highest. AFM investigation of the silane treated fibre surfaces reported in [14] pointed out that the surface topography of S3 treated fibre is quite different. S3 surface appears smooth compared to the surface of S1 treated basalt fibre.

Nevertheless, the question about incorporation of glass components into the silane layer remains. Both Ca and Al are already known to incorporate into the polysiloxane layer [13, 15-18]. Therefore, the normalization of the typical elements found in silane coupling agents (C, N, Si and O) on the amount of Fe seems to be a more significant method to evaluate the surface coverage of basalt fibre. However, our experiments pointed out that the Fe is present to a lesser extent on the unsized basalt fibre surfaces investigated.

3.4 Tensile strength of unsized fibres

Tab. 2. summarizes mean values and Weibull parameters of unsized BAS11 and BAS12 fibres. Tensile strength of unsized BAS12 fibre is considerably higher than unsized BAS11 fibre.

Fibres are manufactured without a sizing. Thus, tensile strength values can be strongly influenced by processing conditions. The protective effect of a sizing during the drawing process is not negligible [14]. In this paper we show that tensile strength values of silane treated or sized basalt fibres are able to attain σ_0 -values up to about 3900 MPa.

Fig. 4. XPS: Overlay of N1s spectra of S1 und S3 treated BAS11 fibre

Tab 2. Mechanical performance of unsized basalt fibres (initial state)

	BAS11	BAS12
Mean [MPa]	1192±617	2457±485
σ_0 [MPa]	1335	2653
m [-]	3	6

Fig. 5. Tensile strength of unsized basalt fibres before and after heat treatment.

3.5 High temperature behaviour

Fig. 5 shows tensile test results after different heat treatments. Tensile strength of BAS12 is decreased. Residual tensile strength after a heat treatment of 5h and a temperature of 500°C is only about 650 MPa, i.e. 26% of initial tensile strength value. In contrast, the absolute tensile strength value of heat treated BAS11 is about 1200 MPa. Moreover, enhanced treatment due to a further increasing of annealing temperature (600°C) did not influence drastically the tensile strength of BAS11, whereas performance of BAS12 seems to be exhausted. Numerous 600°C/5h treated fibres were not able to bear the preload. Therefore, the effective performance is lesser than shown in Fig. 5.

Tab. 3 contains obtained XPS data of high resolution scans. After a heat treatment of 600°C for 5h, the surface layer of both fibres investigated has changed, with a reduced silica content and an increased calcium content within the surface layer.

SEM investigations indicate exclusions on the surface of BAS12, whereas the surface of BAS11 is quite smooth and homogeneous (Fig. 6).

Tab. 3. XPS data of unsized and heat treated (600°C/5h) basalt fibres given as ratio of atom.-concentration

Element (line)	BAS11				BAS12			
	Initial state		Heat treated		Initial state		Heat treated	
	Peak BE	[X]:[O]	Peak BE	[X]:[O]	Peak BE	[X]:[O]	Peak BE	[X]:[O]
Si(2p)	102.6	0.26	101.9	0.18	102.0	0.19	101.5	0.11
Al(2p)	74.5	0.08	74.1	0.05	73.9	0.05	74.0	0.05
Fe(2p)	711.2	0.03	711.0	0.02	711.0	0.03	711.4	0.03
Ca(2p)	348.0	0.04	347.4	0.18	347.5	0.06	347.3	0.20
Mg(1s)	1304.5	0.02	1304.3	0.01	1304.1	0.10	1303.6	0.04

Fig. 6. SEM images after heat treatment 600°C/5h (a) BAS12 and (b) BAS11.

4 Conclusions

In this study unsized and silanized surfaces of basalt fibres were investigated by XPS. In spite of the very complex chemical composition of basaltic glass fibres, the surface is dominated by silica and aluminium. Although, iron oxide is one of the characteristic constituents of the basalt glass structure it is comparatively rarely present on the fibre surface. Therefore, bonding is expected due to reaction of coupling agent and hydroxyl groups on basalt fibre surface.

Surface coverage of silane treated BAS11 fibre was evaluated by ratios of atomic concentrations of characteristic elements of coupling agents and basalt fibre surface. Amino functional silanes investigated show similar values of N/Fe and N/Al ratios, but N1s spectra are different. Regarding XPS results of recent study and results reported in [15], it is concluded that interactions of organofunctional groups with fibre surface, bonding within the siloxane layer, as well as incorporated ions from the glass surface affect the structure and of course the properties of interfacial silane deposition.

The heat treatment experiments indicate that the high temperature performance of basalt fibres preferably depends on their chemical composition. We could show that BAS11's moderate tensile strength level remains after an enhanced heat treatment, whereas that of BAS12 was significantly reduced after same heat treatment. However, it should be noted that the influence of processing conditions was out of the scope of the investigation, but should be considered in future work.

Thereby, for BAS11 a potential of reprocessing basalt fibres is offered. However, the application of reprocessed basalt fibres as secondary raw material requires probably changed concepts for surface modification. XPS and SEM investigations of heat treated basalt fibres show a reduced presence of silica on fibre surface. Therefore the calcium content is increased. In regard of bond formation between silane coupling agent and heat treated basalt surface by a renewed sizing application, it is assumed, that the calcium enrichment on the surface affects bond formation disadvantageously. In order to validate the

assumption, further thorough investigations are underway.

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